

Austria | One Health Surveillance | Avian and swine influenza

Background

- Stakeholder analysis and gap assessment led to four focus areas

Objective

- Setting up an active surveillance program in wild birds
- Setting up a surveillance program for swine influenza in domestic pigs
- Broaden zoonotic influenza surveillance in mammals
- Improve communication and collaboration between veterinary and public health sector during an influenza outbreak

Outcomes & Impact

- Year-round sampling of asymptomatic wild birds and environmental samples
- Established network of stakeholders to foster the submission of samples in domestic pigs
- Surveillance in mammals other than pigs was achieved by testing for influenza in other existing programs
- Horizon Scanning platform established and One Health Working Group for the Surveillance of Zoonotic Influenza – improved collaboration achieved

Lessons learned

- Establishment of networks, collaboration and communication tools improved One Health and trust among stakeholders
- Insufficient awareness of importance of sampling of humans exposed to zoonotic influenza
- Need trust amongst stakeholders and good communication on progress
- Main challenge was lack of regulatory framework for SIV surveillance in humans and pigs at national level

Core messages

- Strategic coordination and structured communication essential for effective zoonotic influenza surveillance
- Stakeholder trust and engagement are foundational
- Flexibility and adaptability are crucial
- Sustainability remains a key challenge. Securing long-term national funding is essential to maintain and build upon current achievements